

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCESAvailable online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

SYNTHESIS OF NEW MONONUCLEAR METAL COMPLEX OF MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE FROM HYDRAZONE SCHIFF BASE: SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION, AND ANTIMICROBIAL STUDY

Gajanan Dongare

Department of Chemistry,

Shri Shivaji College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Akola-444003

Affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444602.MS, India

Article Received: February 2019

Accepted: March 2019

Published: April 2019

Abstract:

The $[Zn(L)(H_2O)]$ complex was synthesized by the condensation reaction of new medicinal significance hydrazone base ligand of 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzylidene)-4-oxopiperidine-1-carbohydrazide (H_2L). The complex was characterized by elemental and spectral techniques such as Infrared, UV-vis, and molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, powder XRD. The ligand and metal stoichiometric ratio was found 1:1 (M:L) in the complex. The spectral, TG data shows tetrahedral geometry toward Zn (II) complex. X-ray diffraction study confirms nanocrystalline nature of metal complex.

Keywords: Mononuclear, metal complex, spectral characterization, X-ray diffraction, Antimicrobial study.

Corresponding author:

Gajanan Dongare,

Department of Chemistry,

Shri Shivaji College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Akola-444003

Affiliated to Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444602.MS, India

phone: +919422712054; email: infogmdongare@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Gajanan Dongare ., *Synthesis Of New Mononuclear Metal Complex Of Medicinal Significance From Hydrazone Schiff Base: Spectroscopic Characterization, And Antimicrobial Study.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(04).

1. INTRODUCTION:

The derivatives of hydrazone-hydrazone are gain enormous importance in pharmaceutical and medicinal field due to its versatile characters playing an important role in synthesis and its application. The researchers have been attracted in large number over the years because of their promising biological activities viz., antimicrobial, anticancer, antituberculosis antiviral and anticonvulsant activities. The most of hydrazone-hydrazone derivatives have been considered as medicinal drugs and have been routinely used in clinics viz., nitrofurazone, furazolidone, nitrofurantoin. Adamantine derivatives are important constituents in medicinal field due to their variable bioactivities. In the year of 1960s, adamantane derivative found in amantadine treated as for antiviral activity. A number of hydrazone and hydrazone derivatives and its Zn(II) complex to find new compounds for the biological activities. As a result, the adamantane derivatives were discovered with enormous biological activities, such as antiviral, antimicrobial, anticancer angiogenesis inhibition, anti-inflammation, 11β hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 1 (11β -HSD1) inhibition, and tyrosinase inhibition activities [1-6].

Scheme1. Synthesis of hydrazone

The azomethine (H-C=N) bond are versatile and playing important role in Schiff bases ligands for coordination chemistry with metal complexes. In recent years, metal (II) complexes of hydrazone Schiff bases have been attracted attention due to their interesting nanocrystalline, antimicrobial activity. The hydrazone Schiff base complexes derived from Salicylaldehyde and its derivatives with primary amines, bearing the ONO donor sets of atoms have particular biological activities [7-10]. The tridentate hydrazone is a special types Schiff base ligand enhancing the peculiar biological activities [11-14]. In

the present research work, new $[Zn(L)(H_2O)]$ was prepared where H_2L is the dibasic tridentate form is reported herein.

2. EXPERIMENTAL:

2.1 SYNTHESIS OF Zn(II) COMPLEX:

The equimolar quantity of a hot solution of hydrazone Schiff base (H_2L) in DMSO was refluxed to the hot alcoholic solution of $ZnCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. The p^H of the solution was maintained 7.5 with a mixture of alcohol and ammonia solution (1.5 ml). The product was recovered by the vacuum filtration and later to wash the small quantity of diethyl ether, and finally by warm ethanol. The elemental data, formula, mol.wt, and molar conductance data of metal complexes are summarised in (Table 1).

2.2 MATERIALS:

The chemicals used in the present research work were of anal. grade from S.D. fine chemicals, and Hi-media. The solvents were dried through the distillation. The silica granules of size 60-100 mesh were used to remove the water molecule from solvents.

2.3 ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS:

Infrared (IR) spectra was recorded on Adv. Bruker spectrophotometer. Elemental (C, H, and N) analysis were made on a on the Carlo-Erba analyzer. The measurement of magnetic susceptibility was performed on a Sherwood magnetic susceptibility balance (MK-1). The 1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectrum of ligand in $DMSO-d_6$ in (TMS) on a Bruker advance 500 MHz spectrophotometer. The (ESI) mass spectrum of hydrazone ligand was measured on micro-mass spectrophotometer. The double beam (1800) Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to record absorption spectra in the range of 200-1100 nm. The simultaneous TG-DTG curves were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (TGA-4000) analyzer in 40 - 800°C with the thermal rate of 20 °C per min in N_2 atmosphere. X-ray diffraction (pattern) were measured on Rigaku-Miniflex (600). The M.P. was determined on electrical melting point apparatus. The molar conductivities of metal complexes were carried out by using Elico conductivity meter-180.

Table1. Analytical data of hydrazone Ligand (H₂L) and its Zn(II) complex

Compounds	Molecular Formula	Mol.wt.	Elemental analysis found (calcd.) %					Molar cond. (Sm ² mol ⁻¹)
			C	H	N	Br	M	
[H ₂ L] Ligand	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Br	340.17	46.02 (45.90)	4.25 (4.14)	12.40 (12.35)	23.70 (23.48)	---	---
[Zn(L)(H ₂ O)]	ZnC ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄ Br	421.55	37.20 (37.03)	3.65 (3.34)	9.98 (9.96)	18.90 (18.95)	15.60 (15.50)	22.30

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 IR spectral characterisation of Zn (II) complex:

Infrared spectroscopy consist of the measurement of the interaction of IR radiation with the compounds by the absorption of radiation. The infrared spectrum of an organic and inorganic compound provides an excellent "fingerprint" which imparts more characteristic to identify number of functional groups such as carbonyl, imino, (C=C), (C-C) bonds in the compound, crystal lattice, halide linkage, tautomerism, enolic and phenolic group of vibration. Zn(II) complexes indicate enolization occurred by the coordination to the metal ion after

deprotonation. The appearance of non-ligand bands about at 824-890 cm⁻¹ inferred that the presence of H₂O molecule and supported to TG analysis and the new bands in the regions 504-575 and 430-461 cm⁻¹ indicating M-O and M-N bond vibrations respectively [15-20]. On the basis of the IR spectral data of (Table 2) and Figure (a) Ligand and (b) Zn(II) complex showing the phenolic-OH deprotonation (monobasic), bonding with N in azomethine and O in carbonyl with metal ions suggested the ligand possesses tridentate moiety, and is mononuclear in nature.

Fig.1 FT-IR spectrum of Ligand

Fig.2 FT-IR spectrum of Zn(II)complex

Table 2. FT-IR spectral data of hydrazone ligand (H₂L) and Zn(II) complex (cm⁻¹)

Compound (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$
(H ₂ L) ligand	1625	1230	950	---	---
[Zn(L)(H ₂ O)]	1576	1380	966	890	504

3.2 Magnetic moment, and UV-Visible spectroscopic studies:

The Zn (II) complex exhibits of the three important absorption of spectral band at 367,294,232 nm are due to intra ligand charge transfer (LMCT and ILCT) at degenerate level. The complex was found diamagnetic at room temperature, suggested and may have tetrahedral geometry to Zn(II) complex [21-24].The absorbance and magnetic moment data Of complex shown in Table (3).

Table 3. Solution conductivity, Magnetic moment, Electronic spectral data of Zn(II) complex

Compounds	Molar cond. (S m ² mol ⁻¹)	Magnetic Moment μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Absorption ($\lambda=\text{nm}$)	Spectral Assignments
[Zn(L)(H ₂ O)]	22.30	Diamagnetic	367 294 232	LMCT ILCT ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$) ILCT ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$)

3.3 X-ray diffraction (powder) study:

The X-ray diffractograms of of Zn(II) complex was performed to determine for evaluation of the types of crystal system, lattice parameters and cell volume and spectra in Fig.(3) and data given in Table 4. The X-ray diffraction pattern was studied using source target CuK α radiation = 1.540559 Å to find out compounds nature, peak intensity, crystallite size, and unit cell dimensions. The Bragg's relation ($n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta$) was

employed for the determination of angle (2θ) and interplanar distance (d) [24-27]. It provides information of unit cell dimensions, characterization of crystalline materials, and identification of fine-grained determination and unit cell dimensions, measurement of sample purity. The crystalline substance possesses the three-dimensional diffraction for X-ray wavelengths similar to the spacing of planes in a crystal lattice. X-ray diffraction is technique for

the study of crystal structures and atomic spacing of inorganic complex compound. Miller indices were calculated and found in expected directions which are supported to the crystal lattice parameter of h, k, l values. The Zn(II) complex crystal system is monoclinic, $a = 7.7800\text{\AA}$, $b = 8.5000\text{\AA}$, $c = 8.0800\text{\AA}$, and

$\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90\text{deg.}$, $V = 534.330\text{\AA}^3$, Space group = P with $Z = 1$ [25-34]. The full width at half maximum intensity (FWHM), the average crystallite particle size Zn(II) complex was 22.12nm which indicating to their nano crystalline nature.

Fig.3 X-ray Diffraction pattern of Zn(II) complex

Table 4- Indexed X-ray diffraction data and lattice parameter of Zn(II) complex

Crystal parameters	Zn(II) complex
Empirical formula	$\text{ZnC}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Br}$
Formula weight	421.55
Temperature (K)	301k
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Scan speed time	10 deg/min.
X-ray	40 kV, 15 mA
Refinement/ Scan range	10-80 deg.
Space group	P 1 21/n 1(14)
a	$a = 7.7800\text{\AA}$
b	$b = 8.5000\text{\AA}$
c	$c = 8.0800\text{\AA}$
α (°)	$\alpha = 90\text{deg.}$
β (°)	$\beta = 90\text{deg.}$
γ (°)	$\gamma = 90\text{deg.}$
Volume (\AA^3)	534.330\AA^3
Z	1
Radiation (λ)	CuK α 1.54059 nm
2 θ range for data collection (°)	11.28 - 63.05
I/Ic (RIR)	0.85
FWHM (β)	0.22-0.81
Average particle size	22.12nm

4. ANTIMICROBIAL STUDY:

The Microbes are very causative components for different types of diseases viz., pneumonia, amoebiasis, typhoid, malaria, and also some diseases i.e tuberculosis, influenza. The infectious diseases caused by the bacteria affect of people and are leading to causes of the death. The antimicrobial agents have been incorporated at a rate exceeding the ability to integrate them into clinical practice. The several advancements in the development of antimicrobial agents, antifungal chemotherapy remains problematic in many cases and search for new antifungal agents continues to be an inevitable task. In spite of the attempts to generate new antimicrobial agents, many problems remain to be solved for currently available antimicrobial drugs. Th hydrazone-hydrazide Schiff bases the most versatile component of these compounds against microbes, and therefore, are useful as microbial candidate in biological sciences.

CONCLUSION:

The hydrazone ligand and its Zn(II) complex was synthesized by single step reaction. The mononuclear complex of the type $[Zn(L)(H_2O)]$ have been characterized by spectro-analytical techniques. Molar conductance parameters inferred that the complexes are non-electrolytic behaviors. The nano crystalline nature of Zn(II) complex was conferred by XRD diffraction techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The author are thankful to SGB Amravati University, authorities for providing necessary facilities of Bruker-IR instrument, and grateful to Principal, Shri Shivaji Science College, Amravati for UV-Vis absorbance spectra.

Funding: This research was not funded by any government or non-government authorities.

Disclosure statement: The author have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

- [1]. Backes GL, Neumann DM, Jursic BS. Synthesis and antifungal activity of substituted salicylaldehyde hydrazones, hydrazides and sulfohydrazides. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2014;22(17):4629-4636. doi:10.1016/j.bmc.2014.07.022
- [2]. Bal S, Bal SS. Cobalt(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes of Novel Schiff Bases, Synthesis, Characterization, and Thermal, Antimicrobial, Electronic, and Catalytic Features. *Advances in Chemistry*. 2014;2014(i):1-12. doi:10.1155/2014/506851
- [3]. Yeo CI, Tiekink ERT. Crystal structure of N-(2-methylphenyl)(propan-2-yloxy)carbothioamide, C₁₁H₁₅NOS. *Zeitschrift für Kristallographie - New Crystal Structures*. 2019;234(3):589-591. doi:10.1515/ncrs-2019-0045
- [4]. Sadhukhan D, Ghosh P, Gómez-García CJ, Rouziers M. A co(II)-hydrazone schiff base single ion magnet exhibiting field induced slow relaxation dynamics. *Magnetochemistry*. 2018;4(4):1-12. doi:10.3390/magnetochemistry4040056
- [5]. Huang W, Li Y, Yong J, Liu Y, Wu D. Hydrazone-based cobalt complexes toward multielectron redox and spin crossover. *RSC Advances*. 2018;8(31):17159-17167. doi:10.1039/c8ra02963f
- [6]. Krishnamoorthy P, Sathyadevi P, Butorac RR, Cowley AH, Bhuvanesh NSP, Dharmaraj N. Variation in the biomolecular interactions of nickel(II) hydrazone complexes upon tuning the hydrazide fragment. *Dalton Transactions*. 2012;41(22):6842-6854. doi:10.1039/c2dt30121k
- [7]. Hameed A, al-Rashida M, Uroos M, Abid Ali S, Khan KM. Schiff bases in medicinal chemistry: a patent review (2010-2015). *Expert Opinion on Therapeutic Patents*. 2017;27(1):63-79. doi:10.1080/13543776.2017.1252752
- [8]. Barnett R. Typhoid fever. *Lancet (London, England)*. 2016;388(10059):2467. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32178-X
- [9]. Bikas R, Ghorbanloo M, Sasani R, Pantenburg I, Meyer G. Manganese(II) complexes of hydrazone based NNO-donor ligands and their catalytic activity in the oxidation of olefins. *Journal of Coordination Chemistry*. 2017;70(5):819-830. doi:10.1080/00958972.2017.1281918
- [10]. Chang EL, Simmers C, Knight DA. Cobalt complexes as antiviral and antibacterial agents. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2010;3(6):1711-1728. doi:10.3390/ph3061711
- [11]. P. J. Naik DVP and PSD. Pelagia Research Library. *Der Chemica Sinica*. 2013;4(4):68-72.
- [12]. Schuster E, Dunn-Coleman N, Frisvad J, Van Dijck P. On the safety of *Aspergillus niger* - A review. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*. 2002;59(4-5):426-435. doi:10.1007/s00253-002-1032-6
- [13]. Meghdadi S, Amirnasr M, Majedi M, et al. Template synthesis, and X-ray crystal structures of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of new unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligands. *Electrochemistry, antibacterial properties, and*

- metal ion effect on hydrolysis-recondensation of the ligand. *Inorganica Chimica Acta*. 2015;437(I):64-69. doi:10.1016/j.ica.2015.08.006
- [14]. Rollas S, Küçükgülmez ŞG. Biological activities of hydrazone derivatives. *Molecules*. 2007;12(8):1910-1939. doi:10.3390/12081910
- [15]. Sadeek SA, El-attar MS, El-hamid SMA. Spectroscopic Investigation of New Schiff Base Metal Complexes. *International Journal of Advanced Research*. 2014;2(7):90-107.
- [16]. Alturiqi AS, Alaghaz ANMA, Ammar RA, Zayed ME. Synthesis, Spectral Characterization, and Thermal and Cytotoxicity Studies of Cr(III), Ru(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) Complexes of Schiff Base Derived from 5-Hydroxymethylfuran-2-carbaldehyde. *Journal of Chemistry*. 2018;2018. doi:10.1155/2018/5816906
- [17]. Neelakantan MA, Marriappan SS, Dharmaraja J, Jeyakumar T, Muthukumar K. Spectral, XRD, SEM and biological activities of transition metal complexes of polydentate ligands containing thiazole moiety. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*. 2008;71(2):628-635. doi:10.1016/j.saa.2008.01.023
- [18]. Deshpande VG, Habib SI, Mahavidyalaya Y. X-Ray Diffraction Study of Transition Metal Complexes of Heterocyclic Schiff Bases. 2016;6(October):934-944.
- [19]. Patil SM, Vadavi RS, Dodamani S, et al. Transition metal complexes of a hydrazone derived from hydralazine hydrochloride and 3,5-di-tert-butylsalicylaldehyde. *Transition Metal Chemistry*. 2018;43(1):65-72. doi:10.1007/s11243-017-0194-0
- [20]. Shaabani B, Khandar AA, Ramazani N, Fleck M, Mobaiyen H, Cunha-Silva L. Chromium(III), manganese(II) and iron(III) complexes based on hydrazone Schiff-base and azide ligands: synthesis, crystal structure and antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Coordination Chemistry*. 2017;70(4):696-708. doi:10.1080/00958972.2016.1274028
- [21]. Taghizadeh L, Montazerzohori M, Masoudiasl A, Joohari S, White JM. New tetrahedral zinc halide Schiff base complexes Synthesis, crystal structure, theoretical, 3D Hirshfeld surface analyses, antimicrobial and thermal studies. *Materials Science and Engineering C*. 2017;77:229-244. doi:10.1016/j.msec.2017.03.150
- [22]. Backes GL, Neumann DM, Jursic BS. Synthesis and antifungal activity of substituted salicylaldehyde hydrazones, hydrazides and sulfohydrazides. *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2014;22(17):4629-4636. doi:10.1016/j.bmc.2014.07.022
- [23]. Bal S, Bal SS. Cobalt(II) and Manganese(II) Complexes of Novel Schiff Bases, Synthesis, Characterization, and Thermal, Antimicrobial, Electronic, and Catalytic Features. *Advances in Chemistry*. 2014;2014(I):1-12. doi:10.1155/2014/506851
- [24]. Nasr, T.; Bondock, S.; Youns, M. Anticancer activity of new coumarin substituted hydrazide-hydrazone derivatives. *Eur. J. Med. Chem*. 2014, 76, 539-548.
- [25]. He, H.; Wang, X.; Shi, L.; Yin, W.; Yang, Z.; He, H.; Liang, Y. Synthesis, antitumor activity and mechanism of action of novel 1,3-thiazole derivatives containing hydrazide-hydrazone and carboxamide moiety. *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett*. 2016, 26, 3263-3270.
- [26]. Nasr, T.; Bondock, S.; Rashed, H.M.; Fayad, W.; Youns, M.; Sakr, T.M. Novel hydrazide-hydrazone and amide substituted coumarin derivatives: Synthesis, cytotoxicity screening, microarray, radiolabeling and in vivo pharmacokinetic studies. *Eur. J. Med. Chem*. 2018, 151, 723-739.
- [27]. Krishnamoorthy P, Sathyadevi P, Butorac RR, Cowley AH, Bhuvanesh NSP, Dharmaraj N. Variation in the biomolecular interactions of nickel(II) hydrazone complexes upon tuning the hydrazide fragment. *Dalton Transactions*. 2012;41(22):6842-6854. doi:10.1039/c2dt30121kHameed A, al-Rashida M, Uroos M, Abid Ali S, Khan KM. Schiff bases in medicinal chemistry: a patent review (2010-2015). *Expert Opinion on Therapeutic Patents*. 2017;27(1):63-79. doi:10.1080/13543776.2017.1252752
- [28]. Barnett R. Typhoid fever. *Lancet (London, England)*. 2016;388(10059):2467. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32178-X
- [29]. Bikas R, Ghorbanloo M, Sasani R, Pantenburg I, Meyer G. Manganese(II) complexes of hydrazone based NNO-donor ligands and their catalytic activity in the oxidation of olefins. *Journal of Coordination Chemistry*. 2017;70(5):819-830. doi:10.1080/00958972.2017.1281918
- [30]. Chang EL, Simmers C, Knight DA. Cobalt complexes as antiviral and antibacterial agents. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2010;3(6):1711-1728. doi:10.3390/ph3061711
- [31]. P. J. Naik DVP and PSD. Pelagia Research Library. *Der Chemica Sinica*. 2013;4(4):68-72.
- [32]. Schuster E, Dunn-Coleman N, Frisvad J, Van Dijk P. On the safety of *Aspergillus niger* - A review. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*. 2002;59(4-5):426-435. doi:10.1007/s00253-002-1032-6

- [33]. Meghdadi S, Amirnasr M, Majedi M, et al. Template synthesis, and X-ray crystal structures of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of new unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligands. Electrochemistry, antibacterial properties, and metal ion effect on hydrolysis-recondensation of the ligand. *Inorganica Chimica Acta*. 2015;437(Ii):64-69. doi:10.1016/j.ica.2015.08.006
- [34]. Rollas S, Küçükgülzel ŞG. Biological activities of hydrazone derivatives. *Molecules*. 2007;12(8):1910-1939.
- [35]. Thiosemicarbazones, semicarbazones, dithiocarbazates and hydrazide/hydrazones: Anti-Mycobacterium tuberculosis activity and cytotoxicity. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 2010, 45, 1898–1905.